

CYCLE PRINCIPLE OF LATIN AND FOREIGN LANGUAGE COURSES IN A MEDICAL UNIVERSITY

Aitmuratova Perkhana Genjebaevna

Assistant teacher at the Department of Languages, Samarkand State
Medical University

Ochilov Abubakr Sheralievich

1st year student of the Faculty Pediatric of Samarkand State Medical
University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10926406>

Abstract. This article is about the fact that medical university students must have various general cultural and professional competencies, including knowledge of historical and medical terminology and the ability and willingness to master one of the foreign languages at the level of everyday communication.

Key words: methods, didactic material, structuring, interactive technologies, optimal method, alternative solutions, professional competencies, situations

Introduction. Studying a foreign language course and the basics of medical terminology at medical institutes, universities and academies is intended, first of all, to prepare a terminologically literate doctor. According to the educational standard, medical university students must have various general cultural and professional competencies, including knowledge of historical and medical terminology and the ability and willingness to master one of the foreign languages at the level of everyday communication, as well as use regulatory documentation adopted in healthcare, study scientific and medical information, domestic and foreign experience on the topic of scientific research. All this is successfully formed when choosing the most optimal methods of training and education.

Main part. Modern pedagogy provides for close interaction between teachers and students at all levels of education, which is achieved through the widespread introduction of interactive technologies into the learning process. In this regard, today the priority is methods where the main attention is paid to the practical development of knowledge, skills and abilities. Thus, when teaching a foreign language and the basics of medical terminology in higher medical educational institutions, methods such as training, programmed, computer training, discussion, case method, business and role-playing games are widely used.

Trainings mean an educational technology for simulating specially specified situations, where students have the opportunity to develop and consolidate the necessary knowledge and skills and generalize their practical experience. Programmed training allows you to achieve a high degree of structuring of didactic material and perform a step-by-step assessment of the degree of its assimilation. In this case, information is presented in small blocks in printed form or on a computer monitor, and students have the opportunity to work at a pace convenient for them, completing tasks that show the degree of mastery of the material. The purpose of the educational discussion is the search process.

At the same time, the teacher creates and maintains a favorable psychological environment in the classroom and ensures the correctness of the conclusions. This method allows students to make maximum use of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, promotes better assimilation of the material they are studying, which is explained by the fact that in a

group discussion they formulate evidence, justify the principles and approaches proposed by the teacher. The purpose of the case method is to consolidate the knowledge acquired by students in the classroom and their examination, in-depth analysis of information, identification of key problems, determination of ways to solve them and formation of an action program. Practical situations can be developed based on descriptions of real events or artificially constructed. The following stages of students' work on a practical situation should be highlighted: familiarization with the situation, identification of problems, analysis of available information, formation of alternative solutions, evaluation of proposed alternatives, preparation of decisions based on the results of consideration of the practical situation, presentation of the results of the analysis, discussion of speeches and summing up.

The business role-playing game method is a personalized game with different, often opposing, interests of its participants. This method helps to develop the following important professional competencies: communication skills, tolerance, ability to work in small groups, independent thinking. A game of this type is a type of simulation associated with the performance of appropriate roles and representing a "substitute" for real situations in everyday life and professional activity. This method is very effective, for example, when conducting a general seminar lesson on the topic "Clinical Terminology". The business role-playing game "Patient and Doctor," organized at such a lesson, can reflect the activities of narrow specialists: therapist, surgeon, obstetrician-gynecologist, otolaryngologist, ophthalmologist, neurologist, endocrinologist, whose roles are played by students.

At the same time, the lesson is planned taking into account the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition, and its structural components are also implemented in accordance with the principles of multiple variable repetition. During the game, students can perform Latin-Russian and Russian-Latin translations of clinical terms, construct them according to terminological elements, explain their general meaning, compare the role of Latin and Greek in medical terminology and in medicine in general, read and write Latin names pathological processes and conditions, term elements denoting the names of sciences, branches of medicine, research methods, analyze terms by term elements and use in speech terms denoting the names of operations, conservative methods of treatment, pathological changes in body functions and physiological processes. In addition, this method promotes the development of creative personality traits, erudition, professional behavior, verbal communication and the acquisition of ethical standards of interpersonal interaction. Interactive teaching methods develop students' ability to identify problems, collect and analyze information, prepare alternative solutions and choose the most optimal one, master communication techniques, and also contribute to the successful formation of their general cultural and professional competencies.

The learning outcome is largely determined by the type of teaching chosen. Not only the process itself, but also the quality of learning depends on what the student focuses on. The advantage of types II and, especially, III is undeniable. The question is how to rebuild the learning process in order to conduct it according to III or at least a combination of III and II types of learning.

After various experiments, we came to the conclusion that the most rational is the cyclical construction of the course, i.e. To . it best suits the purpose of teaching and provides the maximum opportunity to bring the learning process closer to type III. Our task is to prepare a terminologically literate doctor, which means that he must know the law of

construction, first of all, of typical terms, know and be able to work with the main, most common groups of constructive elements. Thus, the teaching tasks force us, firstly, to divide educational material according to the types of medical terms for 3 cycles, secondly, analyze the content of each cycle, highlight the most significant and typical in it, find general patterns and make this the subject of deep and targeted study. Our department followed this path, including in I cycle study of anatomical and histological terminology, 2 - clinical, 3 - pharmaceutical. In this case, grammatical material is studied in relation to each cycle and presented in accordance with the requirements of III and partially II types of teaching.

Cyclic construction immediately revealed a number of advantages. First of all, it became possible to concentrate students' attention on studying only one type of term. This made it possible to develop students' skills on various course topics directly in the classroom, and in some cases, skills. In addition, the identification of constructive elements and general laws for the construction of terms of each type, as well as the general laws for the construction and change of the constructive elements themselves - nouns, adjectives, participles, etc. - makes it possible to explain and consolidate materials to go from the general to the specific, which significantly expands the student's horizons and allows him to transfer the acquired knowledge to new tasks.

Due to expedient differentiation, as well as a generalized presentation, the amount of material and the time of self-study have changed: if previously almost the entire academic year was spent on grammatical material and anatomical terminology, now we fit it into 12 lessons and a general understanding of anatomical terminology, the ability to understand its structure. Students are able to independently construct simple terms with very common categories of words by the 7th lesson. Due to this, the word formation section, which helps to shape the student's professional thinking, has been significantly expanded and deepened.

Conclusions. When constructing a cyclical course, the student sees the advisability of studying grammatical material: when studying anatomical and histological terms - grammatical forms of nouns, adjectives, participles, rules of agreement, when studying pharmaceutical terms with prepositions - the need to study prepositions, when studying clinical terms - the laws of word formation, Latin and Greek term elements. All this develops interest in the subject and increases the awareness of mastering educational material.

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